

Retinoid-Based Innovations in Managing Skin Aging

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Publication Date: 2025/02/22

Abstract: Retinoids, which comprise Vitamin A and its derivatives, are widely used in antiaging and the treatment of psoriasis and acne vulgaris. Retinoids control cell division, proliferation, and death. Anti-wrinkle properties of retinoid compounds include inhibition of metalloproteinase activity, limitation of transepidermal water loss, stimulation of keratinocyte proliferation, and reinforcement of the protective function of the epidermis. Skin aging can be influenced by intricate biological mechanisms that are both endogenous and exogenous. Nowadays, a range of skincare practices can revitalize aging skin. Retinoids are frequently used in anti aging treatment formulations. Externally applied retinoids promote the production of elastin, regulate the renewal of epidermal cells, and raise the number and activity of fibroblasts. As a result, retinoid-containing treatments are being used by an increasing number of people to delay skin aging.

Keywords: Retinoids, Skin-Aging, Vitamin A, Anti-Wrinkle.

How to Cite: Medha Kharat; Shilpa Mishra; Komal Maurya (2025). Retinoid-Based Innovations in Managing Skin Aging. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 10(1), 2822-2832. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14908888>

I. INTRODUCTION

Studies on the prevention of aging have long attracted special attention because aging is a major concern in today's society. The greatest organ in the human body, the skin exhibits clear and noticeable aging. While chronological aging of the human body causes skin to age naturally, photoaging caused by UV radiation is the primary extrinsic factor that speeds up the process because of the reactive oxygen species it produces. [1]

Skin functions include thermal regulation, immunological response, biochemical synthesis, sensory detection, and regulation of water and electrolyte absorption and loss in addition to shielding the body from radiation and the environment. Playing a crucial role is the stratum corneum, which is generated from nonviable corneocytes. Together with filaggrin, the primary protein component of the keratolytic granule, keratin is aligned in the intercrossed disulfidic macrofibres. The intercrossing of involucrin and keratohyalin causes the cells to form a cornified involucre. The intercellular gaps are highly hydrophobic, which is where lamellar lipids gather. Hydrophilic and hydrophobic substances from the outside are blocked by the combination of the hydrophobic intercellular material and the cornified hydrophilic cells.

Age causes the skin's natural renewal process to substantially slow down, resulting in thinner, drier, and less elastic skin. [2]

Retinoids, like glucocorticoids in the middle of the 20th century, have revolutionized dermatology. The FDA authorized topical tretinoin, also known as trans-retinoic acid, as the first retinoid for use in the US in 1971. In 1979, the slightly altered oral cis-retinoic acid gained popularity due to its potent healing properties for severe acne and its alarming potential to cause birth abnormalities. Retinoids have seen continuous development during the past 30 years. Receptor-specific retinoids, such tazarotene and bexarotene, have been available most lately. [3]

Retinoids, as defined by the IUPAC and IUBMB, are compounds composed of four isoprene units arranged in a head-to-tail configuration [4]

Retinoids are a popular dermatological ingredient in cosmetics that are used to treat skin aging, photoaging, psoriasis, acne, and other skin conditions.

Retinoids are mixtures of retinol, retinal, retinoic acid, and tretinoid—naturally occurring, physiologically active forms of vitamin A—as well as synthetic retinol analogs.[5]

Fig 1 Chemical Structure of Retinol (Vitamin A1)[5]

Fig 2 Structural formulas of selected retinoids: retinol (A), retinal (B), 3-dehydroretinol (vitamin A2) (C), and 13-cis-retinol (D) [5]

➤ *Classification of Retinoid*

Retinoids can be divided into different generations according to their structural characteristics and introduction

dates. The following table displays the chemical structures of different retinoids.

Fig 3 Chemical Structures of Retinoids.[2]

➤ *First Generation Retinoids*

The most similar in structure and function to vitamin A are first-generation retinoids, which are found in nature. Retinal, tretinoin (retinoic acid), isotretinoin, retinol, and alitretinoin are some of these. Compared to more recent generations that have undergone modifications to improve their tolerance, the naturally occurring ones are linked to the most harmful effects when used as therapeutic agents. [6]

➤ *Second Generation Retinoids*

The molecular structure of second generation retinoids is identical to that of first generation retinoids, and they are synthetic (man-made).

Among these is acitretin, a metabolite of etretinate. These are more tolerated than first-generation retinoids because they activate all forms of retinoic acid receptors, bind

to them poorly, and are more readily excreted from the body. [6][7]

➤ *Third Generation Retinoids*

The third generation of retinoids, which includes adapalene, bexarotene, and tazarotene, are structurally engineered to bind more selectively and efficiently with certain retinoic acid receptors (such as retinoid x receptors). These are beneficial in treating psoriasis and cutaneous T-cell lymphoma, among other dermatological disorders, since they target particular retinoic acid receptor types. [6]

➤ *Fourth Generation Retinoids*

In comparison to earlier generations, Trifarotene, a fourth generation retinoid, is more effective with less skin irritation and a more bearable safety profile overall because it was made to be even more potent and selective for specific kinds of retinoic acid receptors.[8]

➤ *Mechanism of Action*

Retinoids are useful in controlling the proliferation and differentiation of epithelial cells, which is why they are frequently found in cosmetic products. Through their capacity to permeate through cellular membranes, lipophilic compounds like retinoids produce this impact. They enter cells through certain nuclear receptors, and thereafter, they alter the expression of genes involved in cellular differentiation and proliferation.[9] Topical ROL has anti-aging properties for the skin of the elderly. Topical ROL affects the main skin cell types, including endothelial cells, dermal fibroblasts, and epidermal keratinocytes, by causing alterations in the epidermis and dermis. Through the activation of IFE stem cells and the promotion of keratinocyte development, it increases epidermal thickness. Moreover, ROL improves the dermal milieu by stimulating fibroblasts, which promotes the growth of endothelial cells, which in turn promotes the creation of dermal blood vessels.[10]

Fig 4 Topical ROL Exerts Anti-Aging effects in aged Human Skin.[10]

➤ *Pharmacology of Retinoids and their Receptors*

• *Nuclear Receptors of Retinoids and their Roles in Treatment*

RARs bind all-trans and 9-cis retinoic acid, two important natural vitamin-A derivatives. [11]

Retinoic acid enters the nucleus by attaching to the cytosolic retinoic acid-binding protein (CRABP). Retinoic acid is carried into the nucleus and binds to RAR or RXR, causing receptor heterodimerization and gene transcription.(Figure 5)[11] RARs serve as binding sites for synthetic topical retinoids. RXRs are steroid/thyroid hormone receptors that can exclusively bind to 9-cis retinoic acid, a natural vitamin-A derivative. [11]

Fig 5 Biological Pathway of Natural Retinoids and Target Sites of Synthetic Retinoids.[12]

Retinoids are ligands that bind with RXRs exclusively. RXRs and Retinoic acid receptors (RARs) are classed as class 1 and 2 nuclear receptors, with distinct α , β , and subtype properties.[13] These two receptors function as a dimer. RARs form heterodimers with RXRs, while RXRs can form homodimers with RARs, vitamin D3 receptors, and thyroid hormone receptors. RARs form heterodimers with RXRs, while RXRs can form homodimers or heterodimers with other receptors such as RARs, vitamin D3, and the thyroid hormone receptor.[11] Retinoic acid binds to the RXR receptor, activating the receptor-mediated pathway (e.g., vitamin D3) that RXR dimerizes with.[11] In this case, RXR is a partner actively engaged in the heterodimer.[11]

RXR functions as a silent partner in other situations, meaning that retinoic acid's binding of the RXR receptor has no effect on a response.[11] When there are no ligands present, co-repressors bind dimerized RARs and RXRs.[11] Inaccessible DNA and chromatin condensation are caused by the presence of corepressors. Because it permits the dissociation of corepressors, the binding of natural ligands to these dimers is essential for the development of numerous biological processes. The retinoid-responsive genes' particular DNA sequences are subsequently bound by these heterodimers, activating or repressing the genes that control cell division, apoptosis, and growth.[11][13]

• *Retinoids and Pregnancy*

The growth of the embryo depends heavily on vitamin A, also known as retinol, which is necessary for many cellular functions.[12] By triggering gene transcription in several embryonic sites, retinoic acid aids in the regulation of embryonic development.[14] RXR and RAR possession are

essential for embryonic development, as shown by gene knockout experiments in mice.[15] Only if cells have the right receptors and retinoic acid concentrations are kept within a certain range will they react to retinoic acid. For women who are pregnant or want to become pregnant, the administration of retinoids is either advised against or contraindicated. Retinoids directly affect the embryo, producing aberrant development, as shown by in vitro mice models.[15]

The placenta distributes retinoids from the pregnant mother to the embryo, and the rate at which the intestines absorb retinoids all have an impact on this concentration. [16] Pregnant women may notice changes to their skin at this time. A pre-existing condition's improvement or worsening may be one of these modifications.[16] Since topical treatments are least absorbed and have the lowest potential to harm the developing foetus, they are the most often used method of treating acne during pregnancy.[17]

It is advised to stay away from topical retinoids during pregnancy. Tazotene is classified as category X, while tretinoin and adapalene are in category C. Although topical tretinoin and adapalene are both minimally absorbed, there has been evidence in certain trials that both drugs may be teratogenic when used during the first trimester.[17] There is a possibility of systemic effects when treating big body surface areas, like psoriasis or truncal acne, although studies conducted in the second and third trimester have not demonstrated this.[17] The danger still exceeds the benefits when using agents like tretinoin, even though there is research that suggests the risk may be negligible. As a result, all retinoids should be avoided during pregnancy.[18]

Table 1 Clinically Significant Consideration[12]

Retinoids	Health Indication	Plasma half-life	Ligand receptor binding site	Side effects	Contra-indication	Pregnancy	Formulations
Tretinoin (all- trans retinoic acid)	Acne vulgaris	Normally present in plasma	RAR- α , RAR- β , RAR	Irritation, Local dryness	Hypersensitivity to tretinoin Pregnancy Nursing	Advised not to be used in women pregnant or planning to become pregnant	Stieva-A [®] cream (tretinoin 0.01%, 0.025%, 0.05%) Retin-A [®] cream (tretinoin 0.05%) Retin-A [®] gel (tretinoin 0.025%) Retin-A Micro [®] gel (tretinoin 0.04%, 0.1%)
Adapalene	Acne Vulgaris	7-51 hours (gel)	RAR- β , RAR	Irritation, Erythema Peeling of the skin Local dryness	Hypersensitivity Patients with eczema, seborrheic dermatitis Pregnancy/Planning to become pregnant	Category C	Differin [®] gel (adapalene 0.1%.) Differin [®] cream (Adapalene 0.1%.) Differin XP [®] gel (Adapalene 0.3%.)
Tazarotene	Plaque Psoriasis Acne Vulgaris	18 hr (cream, gel)	RAR- β , RAR-	Irritation of skin Local dryness Erythema Pruritus Worsening of psoriasis	Hypersensitivity Pregnancy/Planning to become pregnant	Category X (contraindicated)	Tazorac [®] cream (tazarotene 0.05%, 0.1%) Tazorac [®] gel (tazarotene 0.05%, 0.1%)
Trifarotene	Acne Vulgaris	2-9 hours	RAR-	Irritation of skin Pruritus	Hypersensitivity Patients with eczema, seborrheic dermatitis, Pregnancy/Planning to become pregnant	Contraindicated	

➤ *Treatments*

• *Retinol*

Many cosmetics and skincare products contain retinol, also known as vitamin A1, vitamin A alcohol, or all-trans retinol, at concentrations of 0.08% or less. Despite being less potent than tretinoin, retinol can reduce photodamage and increase the formation of collagen without irritating the skin like retinoic acid does.[19]

In 1998, Pierard-Franchimont and associates carried out the first controlled clinical experiment with the retinol formulation. After 12 weeks of treatment, they saw a considerable improvement in fine wrinkles caused by the retinol formulation. [20]

Subsequently, in 2000, Varani and associates investigated the impact of topical 1% retinol application on 53 elderly patients (aged 80 years or older) with aging skin. The researchers found that applying retinol for seven days decreased the expression of MMP (matrix

metalloproteinase), collagenase, and gelatinase in the tissue specimens under study, while also increasing the development of fibroblasts and the synthesis of collagen. Therefore, it may be said that retinol should be useful in the management of photoaging and aging.[21]

• *Retinaldehyde*

A precursor to retinoic acid, retinaldehyde is created when human keratinocytes convert retinal to retinoic acid as an intermediary metabolite. Retinaldehyde can be used to treat photoaging because it metabolizes in the skin to retinoic acid, a well-known anti-aging agent, as well as to retinol and retinyl esters, which are typically depleted during photoaging.[22]

Using topical retinaldehyde (0.05%), retinoic acid (0.05%), and a vehicle, Creidi and colleagues performed a randomized, double-blind, controlled experiment. Three French centers collectively recruited 125 patients for this trial. Using the topical treatments was required of the patients for 44 weeks. Using silicone molds of the crow's feet region

on each patient's face, a review was conducted using profilometric techniques at 18 and 44 weeks. Age-related wrinkles and roughness were significantly reduced at eighteen weeks, according to retinaldehyde and retinoic acid outcomes. While still notable, the effect was less noticeable at 44 weeks. In neither of the review periods, the vehicle agent showed a discernible improvement. Throughout the course of the trial, it was also observed that retinaldehyde was less irritating and better tolerated than retinoic acid.[23]

In 1994, Ochando and colleagues investigated the effects of 0.05% retinaldehyde on 32 female volunteers who had mild to moderate photoaging symptoms in an open clinical trial. After four months, there has been a noticeable decrease in coarse wrinkling and surface roughness. Furthermore, there were remarkably minimal side effects linked to retinaldehyde therapy.[23]

- *Tretinoin*

Photoaging can be reversed by tretinoin, often referred to as all-trans retinoic acid (ATRA).

Tretinoin 0.05% cream has been demonstrated to reduce fine wrinkles by promoting the formation of collagen since it was approved for the treatment of photodamaged skin in the mid-1990s.[24][25] Through the use of an animal model of photoaging, Kligman and colleagues (1984) initially proved the effectiveness of tretinoin in treating it. A significant repair zone of new collagen formed in the papillary dermis after 10 weeks of tretinoin treatment for photoaged mouse skin was discovered by the authors. This repair zone also showed a correlation with the effacement of wrinkles. [2]

In terms of retinoid therapy for photoaging, tretinoin is the one that is being researched first.

Studies on tretinoin treatment for longer than six months: In a 22-month trial, assessed the capacity of long-term (greater than six months) tretinoin treatment to sustain improvement in photoaging. During the first four months of the study, all individuals utilized 0.1% tretinoin. From that point on, it was noted that the improvement in wrinkles persisted until the tenth month and then remained stable. As the treatment progressed, the stratum corneum and epidermal thickness returned to normal. The effects of daily use of 0.05% tretinoin emollient cream for a duration of 12 months were examined in a different trial. After receiving tretinoin, the clinical indicators of photoaging significantly improved. After six months, though, the modifications reached their peak, and as seen in the previous study, they then tended to stabilize. The study's overall symptoms of photoaging improved much more when it was extended for six months and applied either weekly or three times a week.[26]

- *Isotretinoin*

Isotretinoin, a cis-isomer of retinoic acid, has a well-documented adverse effect profile that includes xerosis and teratogenicity. It is licensed for oral administration in capsule form for the treatment of acne.[27] 346 patients with photodamaged skin participated in a 6-month, multicenter, randomized, double-blind, vehicle-controlled clinical trial,

which was carried out by Griffiths et al. It was established that using sunscreen and 0.05% isotretinoin together reduced the appearance of the fine lines linked to photoaging of the skin.[28]

For the treatment of photoaged skin, Raza et al. created a hydrogel substitute containing isotretinoin-loaded NLCs (0.05%). An in vivo study was conducted to test the antiaging efficacy of the formulation on extrinsically photoaged mouse skin. The study compared the skin's biochemical and macroscopic features to two commercially available formulations that contained tretinoin and isotretinoin.[29]

- *Alitretinoin*

All subclasses of RARS and RXRS are bound by the retinoid alitretinoin.[30] The topical treatment of Kaposi's sarcoma with alitretinoin gel at dosages of 0.1% and 0.05% is authorized. Only one modest, 16-week open-label pilot trial with 20 participants has examined the effectiveness of 0.1% alitretinoin gel in the treatment of photoaged skin, to our knowledge.[31]

- *Adapalene*

RAR-b and RAR-c receptors are the specific mediating agents of adapalene's action.[12] A prospective, randomized, controlled, masked, two-center, parallel-group study was carried out by Kang et al. to assess the effectiveness of adapalene gel at two concentrations (0.1% and 0.3%) in patients with actinic keratoses and solar lentigines in comparison with vehicle. Adapalene considerably improved the photoaged skin's measured parameters with tolerable tolerability during the course of the 9-month research when compared to the vehicle-treated group.[32]

- *Tazarotene*

Acne vulgaris, photoaging, and mild to severe plaque psoriasis can all be effectively treated topically with tazarotene, a new acetylenic retinoid. [33] In order to determine the effectiveness of 0.1% tazarotene gel, 10 healthy women with mild photodamage to their forearms participated in a pilot study that was double-blind and randomized (Sefton et al. 2000). By using silicon skin surface replicas, it was possible to see that the group treated with tazarotene had significantly less pigmentary mottling, fine wrinkles, and rough skin at the 12-week mark. Furthermore, histological analyses revealed a restoration of keratinocyte polarity and a decrease in keratinocytic atypia.[34][35]

It doesn't undergo isomerization or conformational changes in the skin because of its inflexible polyaromatic structure. According to its ability to bind to different RAR receptors, tazarotenic acid modifies the expression of retinoid-responsive genes, such as those that control cell proliferation, differentiation, and inflammation. Additionally, tazarotene inhibits the aberrant expression of the epidermal growth factor receptor, hyperproliferative keratins, and keratinocytes.[36][37]

- *Seletinoid*

Synthetic retinoid Seletinoid G is selective for RAR- γ . [2] 1% seletinoid G, 0.1% tretinoin, or vehicle formulations

were applied exclusively to the buttock skin of 17 people for four days as part of an in vivo investigation by Kim et al. As a result of the results, selenium G was proposed to be able to repair damaged connective tissue in older skin and prevent UV-induced collagen deficiency in younger skin by having a similar effect on the expression of the evaluated extracellular matrix proteins and connective tissue-degrading enzymes as tretinoin.[38]

- *Retinoid Therapy*

Plenty of studies published in the literature have made attempts to determine the ideal tretinoin concentration in order to maintain a balance between its beneficial and detrimental effects. The cream with a concentration of 0.05% is the usual therapy dose, and it is applied daily. After implementing this treatment plan, fine wrinkle disappearance improves over the course of three months. Alterations in the dermal layer were seen after 12 months of consistent treatment, at which point new collagen fiber formation and elastic material reduction were seen histologically.[39]

Retinoids have had an important effect on clinical practice, especially in dermatology. When Dr. Werner Bollag established his essential research and screening programme in the early 1960s, it was anticipated that retinoids would have an enormous effect on oncology. However, the laboratory and clinical experiences of Bollag and his colleagues in Switzerland, Stuttgart and Orfanos in Germany, contributed to dermatitis documents on both etretinates (Tigason) and isotretinoin (Roaccutane) between 1972 and 1976.[40]

Pharmaceutical research has extensively explored various drug delivery strategies aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of therapeutic agents by altering their physical and chemical properties or reducing associated side effects, ultimately improving patient adherence. Controlled release systems, transdermal patches, implants, submicronic emulsions, and vesicular carriers represent some of the advanced methods highlighting the advantages of innovative delivery approaches.[2]

Two randomized, controlled, double-blinded trials have been conducted, both indicating a more notable enhancement in reducing epidermal wrinkles with a 0.05% concentration of tretinoin compared to 0.01%. Additionally, another study spanning over 8 months compared 0.1% and 0.025% concentrations of tretinoin, revealing no statistically significant variance in epidermal alterations between the two concentrations. [39]

- *Adverse effects of topical retinoids*

The term "retinoid reaction" refers to the most prevalent and common side effect of topical retinoids, which is characterized by erythema, peeling, burning sensation at the application sites, and itch. Retinaldehyde, isotretinoin, adapalene, retinol, and tazarotene are less prevalent than tretinoin and tazarotene.[2]

Photosensitization is the side effect of retinoid therapy, and it usually manifests early in the course of treatment. It is

recommended that patients receiving retinoid therapy refrain from prolonged sun exposure and take preventative steps (such as applying sunscreen) to protect themselves from the sun. But after a few months of treatment, the skin's reaction to UV light returns to normal. When the retinoid is applied near the eye, there have also been isolated reports of irritating conjunctivitis.[41] Because systemic retinoid exposure is known to produce teratogenicity and embryotoxicity, women who are pregnant or of childbearing age should exercise caution when using topical retinoids. However, no incidences of associated teratogenicity have been reported in over 25 years of topical tretinoin use for acne therapy. [42]

- *Formulations*

The retinoid group comprises both natural and synthetic derivatives of vitamin A (retinol). Topically applied formulations containing retinoids exert anti-wrinkle effects by stimulating keratinocyte growth, enhancing collagen production, strengthening the skin's outer layer, preventing collagen breakdown, reducing transdermal water loss, and suppressing metalloproteinase activity. Retinoids function via interaction with retinoic acid receptors (RAR- α , - β , - γ) and retinoid-X receptors (RXR- α , - β , - γ).[1]

- *Nano Formulations*

Novel nanotechnology-based formulations are being developed and tested to improve retinoid efficacy and overcome post-topical application problems. In general, nanotechnology approaches are used to improve the chemical and photochemical stability of the active ingredient, increase penetration, modify its release from the formulation, and achieve satisfactory efficacy with minimal skin irritation. These formulations include lipid-based, polymer-based, metal-based, and other nanosystems (dendrimers, fullerenes, and nanocrystals) . Among them, lipid-based delivery systems (solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), liposomes, and nanoemulsions) are considered advantageous compared to other nanosystems owing to their low toxicity, high drug loading capacity, biodegradability, large-scale manufacturing, and diverse chemical and formulation landscapes.[1]

- *Clinical Trials*

Chemical peels are categorized based on the depth of dermal injury they cause: superficial, medium, or deep. Superficial peels like alpha-hydroxy acids, beta-hydroxy acids, and Jessner solution only affect the epidermal layer without penetrating deeper. Medium peels, such as trichloroacetic acid (TCA) 20–35%, reach into the papillary dermis. Deep peels, like phenols with or without croton oil and TCA 45–50%, target the reticular dermis.[43]

Hevia et al. studied the effects of pretreatment with 0.1% tretinoin cream, used 14-day prior to a 35% TCA peel of the face. The reduced stratum corneum caused by the tretinoin cream application resulted in earlier, more intense, frosting, and a statistically significant increase in reepithelised skin area after 7 days.[44]

Kim and colleagues conducted a study on guinea pig skin to investigate the effects of tretinoin pretreatment

followed by a TCA chemical peel. They observed morphological and histological changes in the skin. The most significant increase in epidermal thickness occurred after 7 days of applying tretinoin. This increase gradually returned to normal levels after 14 days of continuous treatment.[45]

II. CONCLUSION

In the realm of skincare and dermatology, retinoids have emerged as indispensable tools in combating the signs of skin aging. Through their ability to regulate cell proliferation, differentiation, and collagen synthesis, retinoids offer a multifaceted approach to addressing various aspects of skin aging, including wrinkles, loss of elasticity, and uneven pigmentation. The extensive body of research highlighted in this review underscores the efficacy of retinoids in promoting skin rejuvenation and mitigating the both intrinsic and extrinsic aging factors. From first-generation natural retinoids to fourth-generation synthetic compounds, the evolution of retinoid therapy has paved the way for more targeted and tolerable treatment options. Clinical trials have demonstrated the superiority of retinoid formulations in enhancing collagen production, improving skin texture, and reducing the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles. Moreover, advancements in drug delivery systems, such as nanoformulations, hold promise for further optimizing retinoid efficacy while minimizing potential side effects.

While retinoids offer remarkable benefits in skin aging management, it is essential to acknowledge the importance of proper formulation, concentration, and patient education to maximize therapeutic outcomes and minimize adverse reactions. Moreover, ongoing research and clinical trials are essential for refining retinoid-based therapies and exploring novel approaches to address the evolving needs of aging skin. In conclusion, retinoids stand as cornerstone agents in the armamentarium against skin aging, offering patients a potent yet versatile tool to achieve healthier, more youthful-looking skin. As our understanding of retinoid mechanisms continues to deepen, so too will our ability to harness their full potential in the pursuit of skincare excellence.

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